

Contribution of Emotional Maturity, Self Concept, and Social Adjustment in Predicting Academic Achievement of Hearing Impaired Children

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Abstract Due to limited communication, the hearing impaired children tend to have several issues like emotional disturbances, low self confidence, and maladjusted personality which may have negative effects on their achievement also. Keeping this argument in view, present study aims to assess the joint and individual contribution of emotional maturity, self concept, and social adjustment in predicting academic achievement of hearing impaired children. The data was collected from 184 hearing impaired children studying in the Sanket schools of Uttar Pradesh. The findings revealed a significant joint and individual contribution of emotional maturity, self concept, and social adjustment in predicting the academic achievement of hearing impaired children. Among the total variance (16.9%) of the academic achievement of hearing impaired children, the most was contributed by social adjustment (10.1%) and the least by self concept (3.1%). Thus social adjustment and emotional maturity were found to contribute more than self concept in academic achievement of hearing impaired children.

Keywords Hearing Impaired Children, Emotional Maturity, Self Concept, Social Adjustment, Academic Achievement etc.

Introduction One of the challenge before the universalisation of primary and secondary education is to provide equal opportunities of education to the marginal sections of society. Among the marginal sections of the society are scheduled Tribes, schedule castes, women, third gender people and special need children also. The challenge is greater for the inclusion of special need children in the general set up of education. Because of their special needs most of the times and in situations they are educated apart from their normal counterparts. This separation from the normal counterparts causes severe problems in their harmonious growth and development. Maladjustment, low achievement, low self esteem, low self concept, and immaturity are some of the reported problems with the special need children. These problems are more likely to be increase in segregated conditions as in special schools. Also special schools provide the necessary facilities for their particular needs but they keep them separated from the normal society which tends to give negative effects on their development. All the special need children have their own problems but the hearing impaired children feel themselves quite unfit in the normal society because of the limited communication. Due to limited communication, the hearing impaired children tend to have several issues like emotional disturbances, low self confidence, and maladjusted personality which may have negative effects on their achievement also.

Aim of study So, keeping these arguments in view, the present study aims to assess the relationship among emotional maturity, self concept, social adjustment, and academic achievement of hearing impaired children with the help of following objectives:

Objectives of the Study

1. To study the joint contribution of emotional maturity, self concept, and social adjustment in predicting academic achievement of hearing impaired children.
2. To study the contribution of emotional maturity in predicting academic achievement of hearing impaired children.
3. To study the contribution of self concept in predicting academic achievement of hearing impaired children.

4. To study the contribution of social adjustment in predicting academic achievement of hearing impaired children.

Review of Literature

Findings of Albert-Green (2005); Burns (1979); Gerardi (2005); Donohue (2008); Huang (2011); Rukmini and Ramaswamy (2021) support the findings of present study. Dhama (1974) also examined in his study that intelligence, emotional maturity and financial status as element characteristics of achievement of secondary students of Punjab. To support Muley, Patnam, and Vasekar (2003) found high positive correlation between emotional maturity and academic achievement of school going children of urban area. Similarly, Chaturvedi and Kumari (2012) concluded that that emotional maturity has huge impact on academic achievement of male higher secondary students. Further Shanmuganathan and Chinnappan (2014) investigated a critical relation between the emotional maturity and academic achievement of young adult students in his study. Further, Rukmini and Ramaswamy (2021) found that different areas of emotional maturity significantly predict the academic achievement of the students and make significant contributions (3.7% to 1.1%) in emotional stability, independence and academic achievement respectively.

Sandhya (2003) also found positive relationship between self-concept and achievement motivation of high school hearing impaired students. This positive correlation may be due to negative correlation between emotional maturity and anxiety as is claimed by Kumar and Kumar (2015) because anxiety negatively affects academic achievement. Similarly, to support these findings significant correlation between social adjustment and academic achievement of male and female secondary students has been found by Bano and Naseer (2014). Yarmohammadeain, et al(2003); Rivkin, Hanushek, and Kain (2005); Ray and Elliott (2006); Nasir and Lin (2012); Yengimolki, Kalantarkousheh, Malekitabar (2015); Satapathy (n.d.) also support this finding. This is because social adjustment like physical, emotional and intellectual development is a spectrum quantity. One evolves gradually, and improvement obtained through one's experiences and it is the most important indicator of social well-being in adolescents. Adolescents using their social abilities and skills can find their right position among their interpersonal relationships and adult and peer relationship. They can get social acceptance and it, in turn, leads to success in social adjustment. The students who have lower social, emotional and educational adjustment, face various interpersonal problems (Wiener, 2004) and the problems like losing motivation, frustration, anxiety and depression (Sideridis, 2006), these problem, in turn, result in causing failure in academic achievement of the students.

Methodology As the objectives of present research problem are achievable by survey method, the researcher decided to use normative survey method, also known as survey or descriptive survey. Population All the hearing impaired children studying in 6th to 10th classes in special schools of UP government constitute the population for present study. Total 790 students are enrolled in these schools.

Sampling

Keeping in view the objectives of the study, different assumptions of minimum required sample size, population representation, and the limitation of the researcher, a sample of 200 hearing impaired children studying in junior high school and high school level was selected using purposive sampling. Concerning the purpose of the study and maintaining a balance between the number of students studying in the two different levels 130 hearing impaired children were selected from the junior high school classes and 70 (as found in the selected school) from the high school level. Children at junior high school level were selected on the basis of their regularity in the school.

Tools Used To measure the independent variables 'Emotional Maturity Scale' developed by Yashvir Singh and Mahesh Bhargava (2005), 'Self Concept Questionnaire' developed by Raj Kumar Saraswat (year), 'Social Adjustment Scale' developed by Ashutosh Kumar (year) was used. And to gather information about the academic achievement of hearing impaired students previous class result of the selected children was used.

Statistics Used in the Study

Statistical Technique Used-

Out of 200 selected hearing impaired children, 16 did not complete the three tools or completed one or two out of three. So, to get correlation coefficient completely filled three tools by each child i.e. were 184 were used in final analysis. After testing distributional assumptions of normality, linearity of relationship between variables, homoscedasticity of data and outliers of the variables, Multiple Regression Analysis was used to find out the joint and individual contribution of emotional maturity, self-concept, and social adjustment in predicting the academic achievement of hearing impaired children.

Data Analysis

H01: There is no significant joint contribution of emotional maturity, self concept, and social adjustment in predicting academic achievement of hearing impaired children.

Table 1 Multiple Regression Analysis for Emotional Maturity, Self Concept, and Social Adjustment in Predicting Academic Achievement of Hearing Impaired Children

Variable	Degree of Freedom	R	R ²	F	Sig	Regression Equation
Emotional Maturity+ Self Concept+ Social Adjustment+	3, 180	.411	.169	12.191	.000	Y=48.358+.043X1+.062X2+.158X3

Table 2 Coefficients of Regression for the scores of Hearing Impaired Children

Model	Unstandardized Coefficient		Standardized Coefficient	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. error	Beta	Tolerance	VIF
Constant	48.358	3.958			
Emotional Maturity	.043	.014	.214	.910	1.098
Self Concept	.062	.023	.186	.983	1.017
Social Adjustment	.158	.046	.244	.912	1.097

Table 1 reveals that the calculated R & R² values are .411 and .169 respectively for the sample of 184 hearing impaired children. It indicates that 16.9 percent of the variance of the academic achievement of hearing impaired children is contributed by emotional maturity, self concept, and social adjustment. The remaining 83.10 percent of the variance would have been influenced by the other factors that have not been analyzed in this research. Seen from the table 4.21 that regression model is significant at 0.05 level of significance [F (3, 180) = 12.191, p =0.000<0.05]. The calculated F-value is 12.191 that is significant at 0.05 level of confidence discloses that there is a significant joint contribution of emotional maturity, self concept, and social adjustment on academic achievement of hearing impaired children. So, null hypothesis that "There is no significant joint contribution of emotional maturity, self concept, and social adjustment in predicting academic achievement of hearing impaired children", is rejected. According to O'Brien et al. (2007), a tolerance value less than 0.20 to 0.10 shows a multicollinearity problem. Here in the above table 2, tolerance value .910, .983 and .912 shows that there is no problem of multicollinearity in its distribution as the tolerance value is substantially good. The joint contribution of emotional maturity, self concept, and social adjustment in predicting academic achievement of hearing impaired children has been presented in figure- 1

Figure- 1 Showing Joint Contribution of Emotional Maturity, Self Concept, and Social Adjustment in Predicting Academic Achievement of Hearing Impaired Children

H02: There is no significant contribution of emotional maturity in predicting academic achievement of hearing impaired children.

Table 3 Regression Analysis for Emotional Maturity in Predicting Academic Achievement of Hearing Impaired Children

Variable	Degree of Freedom	R	R ²	F	Sig	Regression Equation
Emotional Maturity	1, 182	.267	.071	13.949	.000	Y=63.193+.054X1

Table 4 Coefficients of Regression for Emotional Maturity of Hearing Impaired Children

Model	Unstandardized Coefficient		Standardized Coefficient	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. error	Beta	Tolerance	VIF
Constant	63.193	1.908			
Emotional Maturity	.054	.014	.267	1.00	1.00

The table 3 reveals that the calculated R & R² values are .267 and .071 respectively for the sample of 184 hearing impaired children. It indicates that 7.1 percent of the variance of academic achievement of hearing impaired children is contributed by emotional maturity. The remaining 92.9 percent of the variance would have been influenced by other factors which have not been studied in the present model.

It is seen from the table 3 that the regression model is significant at 0.05 significance level [F (1, 182) = 13.949, p =0.000<0.05]. The calculated F-value 13.949 is significant at 0.05 level of confidence which discloses that there is a significant contribution of emotional maturity in predicting academic achievement of hearing impaired children. Thus, null hypothesis that "There is no significant contribution of emotional maturity in predicting academic achievement of hearing impaired children", is rejected. The unstandardized regression coefficient (b=.054)

indicates that an increase of 1 score in emotional maturity is an increase of 0.054 scores in academic achievement of hearing impaired children. The standardized beta coefficient for emotional maturity is 0.267. This means that an increase of 1 unit of standard deviation in emotional maturity is associated with an increase of 0.267 unit of standard deviation in academic achievement of hearing impaired children. Here in the above table 4, the tolerance value 1.000 and VIF 1.000 show that there is no problem of multicollinearity in its distribution as the tolerance and VIF values are substantially good.

H03: There is no significant contribution of self concept in predicting academic achievement of hearing impaired children.

Table 5 Regression Analysis for Self Concept in Predicting Academic Achievement of Hearing Impaired Children

Variable	Degree of Freedom	R	R ²	F	Sig	Regression Equation
Self Concept	1, 182	.186	.034	6.491	.012	Y=61.896+.062X2

Table 6 Coefficients of Regression for Self Concept of Hearing Impaired Children

Model	Unstandardized Coefficient		Standardized Coefficient	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. error	Beta	Tolerance	VIF
Constant	61.896	3.276			
Self Concept	.062	.024	.186	1.00	1.00

The table 5 reveals that the calculated R & R² values are .186 and .034 respectively for the sample of 184 hearing impaired children. It indicates that 3.4 percent of the variance of academic achievement of hearing impaired children is contributed by self concept. The remaining 96.6 percent of the variance would have been influenced by other factors which have not been studied in the present model.

It is seen from the table 5 that the regression model is significant at 0.05 significance level [F (1, 182) = 6.491, p =0.012<0.05]. The calculated F-value 6.491 is significant at 0.05 level of confidence which discloses that there is a significant contribution of self concept in predicting academic achievement of hearing impaired children. Thus, null hypothesis that "There is no significant contribution of self concept in predicting academic achievement of hearing impaired children", is rejected. The unstandardized regression coefficient (b=.062) indicates that an increase of 1 score in self concept is an increase of 0.062 scores in academic achievement of hearing impaired children. The standardized beta coefficient for self concept is 0.186. This means that an increase of 1 unit of standard deviation in self concept is associated with an increase of 0.186 unit of standard deviation in academic achievement of hearing impaired children. Here in the above table 6, the tolerance value 1.000 and VIF 1.000 show that there is no problem of multicollinearity in its distribution as the tolerance and VIF values are substantially good.

H04: There is no significant contribution of social adjustment in predicting academic achievement of hearing impaired children.

Table 7 Regression Analysis for Social Adjustment in Predicting Academic Achievement of Hearing Impaired Children

Variable	Degree of Freedom	R	R ²	F	Sig	Regression Equation
Social Adjustment	1, 182	.317	.101	20.373	.000	Y=59.878+.206X3

Table 8 Coefficients of Regression for Social Adjustment of Hearing Impaired Children

Model	Unstandardized Coefficient		Standardized Coefficient	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. error	Beta	Tolerance	VIF
Constant	59.878	2.312			
Social Adjustment	.206	.046	.317	1.00	1.00

The table 7 reveals that the calculated R & R² values are .317 and .101 respectively for the sample of 184 hearing impaired children. It indicates that 10.1 percent of the variance of academic achievement of hearing impaired children is contributed by social adjustment. The remaining 89.9 percent of the variance would have been influenced by other factors which have not been studied in the present model.

It is seen from the table 7 that the regression model is significant at 0.05 significance level [F (1, 182) = 20.373, p =0.000<0.05]. The calculated F-value 20.373 is significant at 0.05 level of confidence which discloses that there is a significant contribution of social adjustment in predicting academic achievement of hearing impaired children. Thus, null hypothesis that "There is no significant contribution of social adjustment in predicting academic achievement of hearing impaired children", is rejected. The unstandardized regression coefficient (b=.206) indicates that an increase of 1 score in social adjustment is an increase of 0.206 scores in academic achievement of hearing impaired children. The standardized beta coefficient for social adjustment is 0.317. This means that an increase of 1 unit of standard deviation in social adjustment is associated with an increase of 0.317 unit of standard deviation in academic achievement of hearing impaired children. Here in the above table 8, the tolerance value 1.000 and VIF 1.000 show that there is no problem of multicollinearity in its distribution as the tolerance and VIF values are substantially good.

The individual contribution of emotional maturity, self concept, and social adjustment in predicting the academic achievement of hearing impaired children is presented in Figure- 2.

Figure- 2 Showing Individual Contribution of Emotional Maturity, Self Concept, and Social Adjustment in Predicting the Academic Achievement of Hearing Impaired Children

Therefore, on the basis of the above analysis, it is clear that emotional maturity, self concept, and social adjustment have significant joint and individual contributions in predicting academic achievement of hearing impaired children. Emotional maturity, self concept, and social adjustment have been found significant predictors of academic achievement of hearing impaired children. A comparison of standardized beta coefficients across three predictors (Table 2) suggests that social adjustment is the most significant predictor of academic achievement followed by the emotional maturity and self concept of hearing impaired children.

The regression equation, to predict the scores of academic achievement of hearing impaired children from the scores of their emotional maturity, self concept, and social adjustment, is given below-

$$Y = a + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3$$

$$Y = Y = 48.358 + (.043)X_1 + (.062)X_2 + (.158)X_3$$

Where Y is the predicted value of academic achievement,

a = Constant

β_1 = Beta (Regression) Coefficient of Emotional Maturity

β_2 = Beta (Regression) Coefficient of Self Concept

β_3 = Beta (Regression) Coefficient of Social Adjustment

Findings

1. A significant joint contribution of emotional maturity, self concept, and social adjustment was found in predicting the academic achievement of hearing impaired children.
2. A significant contribution of emotional maturity was observed in predicting the academic achievement of hearing impaired children. This shows that emotional maturity is a significant predictor of academic achievement of hearing impaired children.
3. A significant contribution of self concept was observed in predicting the academic achievement of hearing impaired children. This shows that self concept is a significant predictor of academic achievement of hearing impaired children.
4. A significant contribution of social adjustment was observed in predicting the academic achievement of hearing impaired children. This shows that social adjustment is a significant predictor of academic achievement of hearing impaired children.
5. Among the total variance (16.9%) of the academic achievement of hearing impaired children, the most was contributed by social adjustment (10.1%) and the least by self concept (3.1%). Thus social adjustment and emotional maturity contribute more than self concept in academic achievement of hearing impaired children.

Conclusion Based on the findings of the present study it can be said that early diagnosis of the hearing impaired children would help them better. The future of a child is very much dependant on how s/he performs in her/his academic life and hearing impairment tend to negatively affect her/his emotional maturity, self concept and social adjustment. So if the hearing problem is early diagnosed and preventive and needed assistive measurements are taken from the very beginning, a proper development of these aspects of the child would be feasible. So, the government and policy makers should make necessary arrangements for the diagnosis of deafness and related problems through its different channels like aganwararies, primary schools, and health centres.

Further, teachers teaching hearing impaired children should need to be more sensitive towards the emotional needs of these children. They need to be more careful about the selection of their teaching methods, strategies, and techniques for teaching these children. Accordingly, they should select and mould their motivation strategies and disciplinary approaches for these children. Similarly the parents of hearing impaired children should understand that to help their children in better academic achievement, they should first take care of their emotions and social adjustment along with helping them to focus on their strengths rather than weaknesses. This would help them developing a better self concept and keep them motivated for future.

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